

CHALLENGES OF MENTAL HEALTH DISORDERS OF MOTHERS AND IMPLICATIONS ON INFANTS' BEHAVIOUR IN AKWA IBOM STATE

Udom Sunday Daniel¹

Victor E. Ben²

¹Department of Sociology and Anthropology

Akwa Ibom State University

udomdaniel@aksu.edu.ng

²Department of Sociology and Anthropology

University of Uyo, Uyo

ABSTRACT

This descriptive research investigated the implications of mother's psychiatric disorder on her infant's behaviour in Akwa Ibom State. It sought to evaluate the relationship between the depressed mothers' attitude and the behaviour of their infant. The study made use of Strain Theory as its theoretical framework. The study was conducted within the Eket Psychiatric Hospital in Ikot Ebiyan and University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo. A total of 20 participants were considered for the study due to availability as at the time of the study. Pie chart was used by the researchers for descriptive analysis of the data collected from the field. Findings of the study revealed that psychiatrically ill or mentally disordered mothers' self-evaluations are not always concordant with the emotional quality of their interactions with their infants, some areas of maternal malfunctioning may change more easily than others therefore causing a serious challenge on the behaviour of infant, and children of psychiatrically disordered mothers find it difficult to mingle with their peers even after they are grown as a result of the stigma gotten from the society as a result of the health experience of their mentally disordered mothers. The researchers recommend government partnership in the treatment of mentally impeded mothers to avert its cost implications on the patients and families as well as the challenges on their infants.

KEYWORDS: Mental health, Mentally disordered mothers, Infants' behaviour and Psychiatric.

INTRODUCTION

A study by Tronik *et al* (1997), indicate that infants are exquisitely sensitive to the emotional states of their mothers and caregivers especially if the experience occur in the earliest state of their life. This is fundamental to understanding the effects of maternal psychiatric illness, of mothers such as depression and anxiety, on infant development. Suleiman (2016) opined that In Nigeria, an estimated 20%-30% of the population suffers from mental challenges. Studies by Abdulmalik *et al*, (2019) also reveal that only one out of every five persons who suffer from mental health problems can access any care (Abdulmalik *et al.*, 2019) while, less than 3% of the Nigerian government health budget goes to the prevention and treatment of mental health problems, with most of the funds allocated for the operational cost of dilapidated mental health facilities rather than the patients (Anyebe *et al.*, 2019; World Health Organization, 2019). However, mental healthcare treatment options in Nigeria are scarce and expensive (Anyebe *et al.*, 2019; Madhombiro *et al.*, 2021), and about 75% of Nigerians depend on their income for the payment of bills (Aregbeshola and Khan, 2020). Not only is the lack of public health resources a significant challenge to the public in Nigeria, but more challenging on women's mental state during their pre- and post-natal periods and their infants. Consequently upon the above maternal mental health has become a significant health concern that carries a serious disease burden and adverse effects for both the mother and child

Depression is said to be a common natural health problem which affects about 19%-25% of women in their maternal periods (Gelaye *et al.*, 2016), and majority of the women affected by this problems are those from low and middle-income countries, (Gelaye *et al.*, 2016). Indeed, it is challenging to generalize epidemiological data regarding the prevalence of maternal mental health problems as it is unevenly distributed across the world regions thus, low and middle-income countries and societies like Nigeria and Akwa Ibom State contribute the least data due to the paucity of research. Therefore, it could be argued that data collected in low and middle-income countries like Nigeria on the quality of care services-users received is often left unnoticed and perceived as poor quality with significant information gaps on the safety. In Nigeria and other third world countries, data on disease prevention and evidence-based treatment are scares. (Weinberg and Tronick 1997; Udom, 2016). Among the Akwa Ibom people, many factors like faith healing, divinations, herbalist patronage and poor patronage of orthodox medicine influence mental health treatments (Esen, and Peters, 2023¹; Esen and Peters, 2023²; Esen and Peters, 2023³ and Esen, Peters and Esen, 2023). On the effects of on maternal and infant behaviour studies, indicates that in each communicative domain-face, voice, and touch- the quantity, quality, and timing of depressed mothers' social and affective behaviour are distorted in ways that contrast sharply with the behaviour of non-depressed mothers. As distortions of maternal behaviour are related to compromises in infant social, emotional, and cognitive function, (Cohn J. *et al* 1990, Field T *et al* 1990) much of the research that evaluates the behaviour of depressed mother has treated these mothers as if they form a homogeneous group. The picture, however, is more complicated and research suggests

that the behaviour of depressed mothers too is heterogeneous and maternal depression does not have a singular compromising effect on the infant.

STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

Several researchers have revealed that some depressed mothers' behavior do have the health of the children affected. Cohn and Tronick, (1989) for example, describe depressed mothers who are disengaged and withdrawn when interacting with their infants as they are not having the capacity to give effective care, noting that these withdrawn mothers engage in little play, talk only rarely to their infants using mother eye, and show flat and sad outlook while other mothers are more intrusive. They express anger directed at their infants and interfere with their infants' activities. This is not the same with non-depressed mothers who are able to mobilize sufficiently to interact positively with their infants. Though Cohn J. et al (1990) indicates that not all depressed women function poorly as parents, the author does not indicate whether the “positive” depressed mothers represent a subgroup of mothers with less severe and chronic depression and may not experience an impairment in interactional skills. Women with more severe and chronic depression are seen as been unable to compensate for a worsening in their mood. It is also unclear whether the “positive” depressed mothers have infants who are temperamentally more easy-going and better able to elicit a positive interaction from the mother. It is on the strength of the above therefore that this study seek assess the implications of mother's psychiatric disorder on her infant's behaviour and to evaluate the relationship between the depressed mothers' attitude and the behaviour of their infant.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To assess the implications of disadvantaged health status mothers on the behaviour of their infants.
2. To evaluate the relationship between depressed mothers attitude and the behaviour of their infants.
3. To offer solutions toward addressing mental health disorder of mothers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Gelaye *et al.*, (2016) associated depression in mothers with many adverse outcomes, including poorer psychological health, disturbances in neurocognitive and physical development for the mother as well as depression on the child of the depressed mother. In Nigeria, where factors such as poor social environment for child growth and poor-nutrition are more prevalent (Jidong *et al.*, 2021), contributing to the poor development and maintenance of maternal mental health patients as well as distortions in the child's development process (Adewuya *et al.*, 2007). Common symptoms of depression such as poor concentration, sleep and appetite disturbances, low mood and loss of interest are factors that can significantly impact on the mother's capacity to fulfil the demands of her child's emotional

and physical needs. Consequently, a mother who suffers from a mental health problem may be less responsive to her child's cues, as explained in Attachment theory. Taken together, evidence generally supports the idea that infants who have depressed and/or anxious mothers may have difficulty expressing emotions resulting from their relationship in-turn impede their social management, enhancing the risk for later development.

This shows that infants whose mothers had higher levels of anxiety and symptoms of depression may impact the parts of a baby's brain that plays an important role in healthy brain behaviour. According to Kinarid (1995), on the basis of maternal ratings, children of depressed mothers have been found to be more likely than those of non-depressed mothers to have internalizing and extenuating problems and to have a higher rates of major depression, conduct an oppositional, anxiety, and substance used disorders.

Anxiety, Maternal and Infant Functioning

Literature on malfunctioning and mental recession of mothers avail on older children and on panic disorder to the exclusion of other anxiety disorders rather on the effects of anxiety on infant development imbalance despite the paucity of findings, the available research suggests that maternal anxiety, like depression, may have a powerful developmental effect on children. Increased rates of psychiatric difficulties have been reported in the children of mothers with anxiety disorders. Weissman *et al.*, (1984) for example, in their studies reveals that 6- to 7-year –old children with a parent who has panic disorder were three times more likely than control children who experience anxiety disorders. Several studies also report higher rates of behavioural inhibition in the children of mothers with panic disorder. (Biederman, 1993).

Behavioural inhibition is defined by Kagan, Mullen, Reznick, (1993), as a temperamental tendency to withdraw from novelty and unfamiliar situations. Research by Mullen *et al.*, (1993) indicates that 10% to 15% of American children are inhibited and predisposed to be irritable as infants and shy, fearful, quiet, and introverted at older ages. Rosenbaum *et al.* (1998) found that 85% of the children (ages 2-7) of parents with panic disorder, were rated as behaviorally inhibited, compared with 50% of the children of parents with depression and 15% of the children whose parents had neither panic disorder nor depression. Biederman *et al.* (1993) further found higher rates of multiple anxiety disorders (two or more anxiety disorder per child) in children described as behaviorally inhibited. These rates increased markedly over a period of 3 years when the children were reassessed. However to Biederman *et al.*, (1993), caution the majority (approximately 70%) of inhibited children to develop an anxiety disorder. and behavior inhibition may be one of the several risk factors contributing to the ontogeny of later psychopathology. Children of mothers with panic disorder may also have a higher rate of insecure attachment to the mother. Eighty percent (80%) of the preschool children in a study by Manassis *et al.*, (1994) were classified as insecurely attached to their mothers because of their state of health. Manassis *et al.* (1994) indicates that the children of mothers with panic disorder are at risk for developing anxiety disorders themselves and that inhibited temperamental characteristics or attachment

difficulties may be early risk factors.

Depressed Mothers' Effects on Children's Association and Behaviour

Long-term exposure to mothers' depression according to Fergusson and Lynskey (1993) in Najman, Nikles, Spence, Bor, Michael, Brocque, Margaret (2002) is more likely to be associated with childhood behaviour problems than is short-term exposure. One view argues for a cause-effect association emphasizing the biological and or environmental transmission of mental illness from the mother to the child. Another view in accounting for the observed effects, noted that depressed mothers may have a 'cognitive bias' which distorts their judgements including the behaviour of their children. Taken together, evidence generally supports the idea that infants who have depressed and/or anxious mothers may have difficulty, expressing emotions resulting from their non-optional social development and this may impede their social engagement, enhancing the risk for later development of depression and anxiety. The variability in the prevalence estimate across studies of mother's psychiatric disorders influence on the Children's behaviour is partly disadvantages, unique and pregnancies, low empathy, and poor social support from the partner and environment (Fisher, Mello, Patel, Rahman, Tran, Holton, 2012). However, the authors further noted that being younger during first pregnancy, becoming pregnant without been married thus lacking intimate partner empathy and support having hostile in-laws, experiencing intimate partner violence, having insufficient emotional and practical support all transfer hostile relationship on children by their affects mother's fisher *et al* (2012) concluded that mothers psychiatric disorders are more prevalent in low and lower middle-income countries, particularly among poorer women who cannot afford medical services than among rich women. This however affects the behavioural pattern of their children, identifying the socialization defect as the cause.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study adopts the attachment theory. The attachment theory describes a psychological system motivated by innate behaviour to seek support from others, particularly in times of needs. This is the premise on which this study is built. The theory explains that children needs emotional stability and for this to be possible they needs to be properly attached to their caregivers or mothers. According to the theory, nowhere the child experienced an imbalanced upbringing due to poor attachment, he is bound to have behavioural disorder.

Attachment theory describes a psychological system motivated by innate behaviour to seek support from others, particularly in times of need (Ainsworth, 1979; Bowlby, 1969; Yip *et al.*, 2018). Deducing from the Healthcare utilization Model in Peters and Daniel (2024), the model noted that predisposing factors – enabling factors – needs factors and healthcare services have implications on the attitudes and behaviours of the sick and attached person –in this case the mother with psychiatric disorder and the infant behaviour. Where the needs fails and healthcare services not utilized; Udom and Peters (2024) noted that the

consequences will occur; health challenges or havoc that will affect the mother and the baby attachment. This however occurs as a result of the socio-psycho attachment they both share. It is worthy to note that children of depressed mothers or caregivers have higher tendency to display avoidant or disorganized forms of behaviour compared to children from non-depressed mothers (Martins and Gaffan, 2000; Toth *et al.*, 2009). Although these associations seem to produce modest results which may be related to other inter-correlated factors, such as marital conflicts and lack of social support; however, the theory suggest that maternal care received at early childhood influences the child's later, emotions, behaviors and wellbeing (Rosmalen *et al.*, 2015; Yip *et al.*, 2018) as they grow. Attachment theory aligning with Udom and Tahirih (2024) Behaviour option theory noted that environmental, personal, income status, illiteracy level, belief system as some major factors in behavioural determination. It proffers therefore that mental deficiency of patients should be cared for to enable proper mother-child attachment and relationship.

METHODOLOGY

In order to achieve the purpose of the study, the survey design was used. It was adopted for the study because the variables that are considered in this work had already existed. Udo and Joseph (2005) opined that survey design helps to identify the relevant information in a study since it helps to describe what is involved, analyse records and interpret the information. It also involves comparisons or contrasts and attempts to describe the relationship which exists between the variables involved in a study. The study area is Akwa Ibom State, which is located in the Southern part of Nigeria, but for financially easement and time, Eket Psychiatric Hospital, and with by Psychiatric unit all of Akwa Ibom State were sector for the studying. The Eket psychiatric hospital is located in Ikot Ebiyan, Eket Urban Ward 3, Eket Local Government Area, while University of Uyo Teaching Hospital, Uyo is located in Uyo Local Government Area. 20 respondents 10 each from the two hospitals comprising of medical personnel and patience care givers where selected for the study.

RESULTS

Source: Author's Survey (2021)

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The data collected for this work was basically primary and secondary data which was obtained from patients' medical records, magazines, textbooks and other research materials, and interviews with particular parents.

- Do you know of any mother or caregiver who is mentally deformed? YES
- Is it true that children of mentally deformed mothers are affected by their relationships with them? YES
- Upon treatment, do Psychiatric mothers completely come out of their illness?
- Are Psychiatric mothers properly attached to their children? YES

These results indicate that psychiatrically ill or mentally disordered mothers' self-evaluations are not always concordant with the emotional quality of their interactions with their infants. A similar discordance was reported by Martins and Goffau (2000) on women of mental imbalance, which shows that after an acute psychiatric episode, depression and anxiety are over, mothers continue to show interactive and emotional difficulties with their children (WHO, 2019) which in turn has negative effects on the cognitive development of the infant.

The findings suggest that some areas of maternal malfunctioning may change more easily than others therefore causing a serious challenge on the behaviour of infant. However, self-perceptions have been identify as the first area to improve as a result of treatment as an effort to correct the disorder. Changes in interactive behavior and intimate relationships, on the other hand, maybe less easily amenable to treatment and/or remission.

Mother-infant relationships develop stable characteristics based on effective mothers' and infants' interactive history (Tronick and Weinberg, 1997), thus were both mothers and infants have a cordial interactive relationship they are bound to have a balance social behaviour with each other following predictable patterns.

The finding further indicated that children of psychiatrically disordered mothers find it difficult to mingle with their peers even after they are grown as a result of the stigma gotten from the society as a result of the health experience of their mentally disordered mothers. They are rather withdrawn and tend to be self-isolating in most cases. For a change to occur in the mother-infant relationship, the mother's perceptions of her infant and of herself as a parent as well as her interactive behaviour with the infant must change.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The infant's interactive representations and behaviour must also change, given the reciprocal nature of interactions and the infant's active role in shaping relationships. Thus change takes place at different levels, though often a slow and through a difficult process. However, deducing from Daniel and Ben (2024) who argued that women's rights and well-being should take precedence over national interest, the study recommended timely awareness, sensitizing of partners and family members on the urgent need for treatment of psychiatric mothers of their disorder, infections and other diseases to avert its further dangers and their challenges. The study also discourages untimely and teenage pregnancy as faulted by Daniel and Peters (2024) as it equally affects the mental alert of mothers, recommending government partnership in the treatment of mentally impeded mothers to avert its cost implications on the patients and families as well as the challenges on their infants.

REFERENCES

- AbdulMalik, J.A (2019). Depressed Mothers. *Journal of mental health assessment*, (2019).
- Adewuya A. (2007). Prevalence of major depressive disorder and a validation of the beck depression inventory amongst Nigerian adolescent, *National Study Journal*.
- Aregbesola E. and Khan, O. (2020). Out of pocket health care spending and its determinants.
- Ben V. E. and Daniel, U. S. (2023). Disease, Prevalence and Infant Mortality in the Rural Areas of Akwa Ibom State: AKSU Annuals of Sustainable Development, Volume 1, Number 2, December, 2023, Issue 3027 – 0499.
- Ben V. E., Daniel, U. S. and Peters, M. I. (2023). Estimation of Life Experiences among Pregnant Women during Covid-19 in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Culture and Society*. Maiden Edition, Issue 2 Nov. 2023.
- Biederman J, Rosenbaum JF, Bolduc-Murphy EA, et al. A 3-year follow-up of children with and without behavioral inhibition. *J. Am Acad Child Adolescent Psychiatry* 1993;32;4:814-821.
- Biederman J, Rosenbaum, J. F. and Hirshfeld, D. R. (1990). Psychiatric correlates of behavioral inhibition in young children of parents with and without psychiatric

- disorders. *Arch Gen psychiatry* 1990;47:21-26.
- Cohn J, Campbel SB, Matias R, (1990). Face-to-face interactions of postpartum depressed and non-depressed mother-infant pairs at 2 months. *Dev psychol* 1990;26:15-23.
- Cohn, J. F. and Tronick, E. Z. (1989). Specificity of infants' response to mothers' affective behaviour. *J Am Acad Child Adolescent psychiatry* 1989;28:242-248.
- Daniel U. S. and Udousoro T. E. (2024). Determinants of Preference of Abortion and Non-Utilisation of Family Planning Services among Women of Child bearing Age in Rural Communities of Uyo Local Government Area, Akwa Ibom State. *International Journal of Culture and Society*, Volume 2, Issues 2, April 2024.
- Daniel, U. S. and Ben, V. E. (2024). Fertility Behaviour and Family Size Preference of Women with Chronic Infection: Analysis of Aba Women. *International Journal of Culture and Society* 2(1):60-70 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11060664>.
- Daniel, U. S. and Moses, I. P. (2024). Teenage Mothers and Pregnancy Related Challenges in Traditional Societies of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Culture and Society*. Volume 2, Issue 2, April, 2024.
- Esen, R. E., Peters, M. I. and Esen, Ubongabasi Akpan (2023), Divination and Mental Health Seeking Behaviour of the Ibibio People of Southern Nigeria: A Qualitative Exploration. *International Journal of Culture and Society* Zenodo, Switzerland, Maiden Edition (1): 18 – 29
- ¹Esen, R. E. and Peters, M. I. (2023). Mental Illness and the Panacea of Orthodox Medicine Patronage among Ibibio People of Southern Nigeria. *Global Journal of Communication and Humanities* (GJCH). Eleviv Publishing Group, USA. 2(1): 2 -16
- ²Esen, R. E. and Peters, M. I. (2023). Herbalists and Mental Health Seeking Behaviour among the Ibibio People of Southern Nigeria. *Social Sciences and Management International Journal* Eleviv Publishing Group, USA. 4(1): 1 -14.
- ³Esen, R. E. and Peters, M. I. (2023). Faith Healing and Mental Illness among Ibibio People. *Ripple of Culture: Journal of Anthropology*. 2(1): 50 – 63.
- Fergusson, D. M. , Lynskey, M.T. (1993). The Effects Maternal Depression on Child Conduct Disorder and Attention Deficit Disorders. *Soc. Psychiatry Psychiatr Epidemiol* 28:116-123.
- Field T, Healy B, Goldstein S, et al. Behavior-state matching and synchrony in mother-infant interactions of non-depressed versus depressed dyads. *Dev Psychol* 1990; 26:7-14.
- Fisher, J. Mello M. C., Patel V. Rahman A, Tran T., Holton S. (2012). Prevalence and Determinants of Common Perinatal Mental Disorders in Women in Low and Lower-Middle Income Countries; A Systematic Review.
- Kinard E. M. (1995). Mother and Teacher Assessments of Behaviour Problems in Abused Children. *J. Am Acad Child Adolescent Psychiatry* 34:1043-1054.
- Gelaye B. epidemiology of maternal depression, risk factors and child's outcome in low and middle income countries 2016.
- Lyons-Ruth K, Zoll D, Connell D, et al. The depressed mother and her one year-old infant: environment, interaction, attachment, and infant development. In: Tronick Ez, field T, eds. *Maternal Depression and Infant Disturbance: New Directions for Child*

- Development, no. 34. San Francisco, Calif: Jossey-Bass; 1986:61-82.
- Manassis K, Bradley S, Goldberg S, (1994). Attachment in mothers with anxiety disorders and their children. *J Am Acad Child Adolescent Psychiatry* 1994;33:81106-1113.
- Manassis K, Bradley S, Goldberg S, (1995). Behavioral inhibition, attachment and anxiety in children of mothers with anxiety disorders. *Can Psychiatry* 1995;40:87-92.
- Martins, G. and Gaffan, H. (2000). Effect of early maternal depression on patterns of mother-infant attachment.
- Mullen M, Snidman N, Kagan J. (1993). Free-play behavior in inhibited and uninhibited children. *Infant Behavior and Development* 1993;16:383-389.
- Peters, M. I. and Daniel, U. S. (2024). Determinants of Healthcare Services Utilisation among the Elderly in Mbo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Culture and Society*. Volume 2, Issues 2, April, 2024.
- Rosenbaum, J. F., Biederman, J. and Gersten, M. (1988). Behavioral inhibition in children of parents with panic disorder and agoraphobia: a controlled study. *Arch Gen Psychiatry* 1988;45:463-470.
- Rosenbaum, J. F., Biederman, J. and Hirshfeld, D. R. (1991). Behavioral inhibition in children: a possible precursor to panic disorder or social phobia. *Journal of Clinical Psychiatry* 52(11):5-9.
- Suleiman D. mental health disorder in Nigeria, (2016) Tronick EZ, Winberg MK. Depressed mothers and infants: failure to form dyadic states of consciousness. In: Murrau L, Cooper PJ, eds. *Postpartum Depression and child development*. New York, NY: Guilford Press
- Udom, S. D. (2016) Population Growth and Social Services Provision in Uyo Senatorial District of Akwa Ibom State, Research Gate.
- Weinberg MK, Tronick EZ. Maternal depression and infant maladjustment: a failure of mutual regulation. In: Noshpitz J, ed. *The Handbook of child and Adolescent Psychiatry*. New York, NY: John Wiley and Son; 1997.
- Weissman MM, Leckman JF, Merikangas KR, et al. Depression and anxiety disorders in parents and children: results from the Yale Family Study *Arch Gen Psychiatry* 1984;41:845-852.
- World Health Organization, Mental Health Summit (2019).